

TEACHING THE NOVEL OF THE PAST DAYS THROUGH INTERACTIVE GRAPH ORGANIZERS

Tulenova Farida

Teacher 197 school Tashkent

Interactive graph organizers - study in the process mental processes demonstrative present reach , or different by doing when we say , it is placed to the goal in reaching help giver drawing , table , graphs set _ Graph organizers with more work _ in terms of interactive education methods belongs to being their _ between differences no _ If the graph organizers teacher ready , filled without otherwise , the tool the task of students campaign to the subject circle knowledge strengthening and thinking development in order to method if used his wife performs _

Lesson transition comfortable and live to be for different demonstrative weapons work exit necessary will be Of them own on time and in place to use to act need _ Complicated the subject students to his mind easily deliver let's read together for , blist , venn diagram , case study such as from the organizers is used .

"LET'S STUDY TOGETHER" TECHNIQUE

Collaborative study: the study group is divided into small groups. Each small group becomes an expert in one area of the subject being studied and teaches others.

The structure of the process of organizing work in groups using the "Let's study together" technique

1. Groups of 5-6 students are formed, and they are named based on the suggestions of students.
2. Each group is given one task - a part of the general topic, on which the whole study group works, and expert sheets are presented to them.
3. A common task is distributed within each group.
4. Everyone performs an individual task.
5. Mini -lectures of all group members will be heard. They form a general result and prepare it for presentation.
6. The leader presents the results of group work.

The rule of working in groups

Listen carefully to the questions.

Take an active part in group work, approach assigned tasks responsibly.

If you need help, definitely reach out.

If you need help, by all means help.

Everyone must participate in the evaluation of the results of group activities.

We need to know for sure:

A. We learn by teaching others.

B. We are in one ship: either we sail together or we sink together.

Readers will realize in the process of analysis and interpretation that Abdulla Qadiri's writing talent and artistic potential are manifested in the novel "Gone Days". At the same time, readers should pay attention to the fact that the author has achieved the goal he set for himself in the novel "The Past Days" by transferring the traditional literary and folk artistic way of thinking to a new style - a realistic narrative method. It would be appropriate if Abdulla Qadiri's original writing edge turned to a new form - the novel genre, realizing the need to create a new

one in line with the times instead of an outdated means of expression. In a word, it is necessary to instill in the minds of readers that the novel "O'tkan kunlar" is an epic of its time in a new form. Teaching it using various interactive methods, in particular, "Let's read together" technique, blist game, case-study methods, teaches students to work and think. Therefore, we will first analyze the writer's novel "The Past Days" using the "Reading Together" technique below.

O'quv topshiriq № 1

“O'tkan kunlar” romanida ro'y bergan chigal

O'quv topshirig'i № 2

Yozuvchining obraz yaratish mahoratini Kumush va

Lennat xole obrazlari misolida qiyoslang.

O'quv topshirig'i № 3

Kumush portreti aks etgan lavhani o'qing va badiiy tasvir vositalarini toping.

O'quv topshirig'i № 4

Portret tasvirini yaratishda Qodiriy qahramon yuzini,

O'quv topshirig'i № 5

Otabek ota-ona rizoligi uchun bosh egib to'g'ri qildimi? Uning o'rnida siz nima qilgan bo'lardingiz?

BLK

The blist game for students is distributed to each student separately.

Rules of the game: the questions are placed in the boxes under the number 1. Students' answers are given in the boxes under number 2. In this case, the student will mark "+" for each answer that he considers to be correct, and "-" for each answer that he considers to be incorrect. The correct answers given by the teacher are marked in the boxes under number 3. The signs "+", "-" are also used in this. In the cells under the number 4, a mark is set for each correct and incorrect answer, and these marks are placed in the column of marks allocated for the answer.

Abdulla Qadiri's novel *Otkan kunlar?* "

1	2	3	4
S avalos	Student response	Correct answer	Reserved for reply ba ho
Genre of the work			
Style			
Construction of the work			
Components of the work			
Images			
The language of the work			
Image of nature			
National mentality			
Character			
A matter of skill			

This through , " Gone days " of the novel nationality , in particular , in people fine , k ' zga non-disposable aspects obvious manifestation b dies . _ The issue of nationality in literature has always been the focus of attention of literary scholars and researched. It is not for nothing that *Otkan Kunlar* is recognized as the first Uzbek national novel. Skillful use of the possibilities of the Uzbek literary language, reflecting national characters and national spirit; It is a huge creative achievement of the writer that he managed to describe the scenes of national life, customs, and manners from the point of view of national culture. From the very beginning of the work, it is known that the author set as his main goal to bring the national spirit characteristic of Uzbek folklore and classical literature into the novel genre. By reflecting the national spirit and national thinking in his work, the writer embodied the national way of life, the problems of domestic life, and achieved the revival of characters such as Otabek, Kumush, Mirzakarim Kutidor, Yusufbek Haji at the level of national characters.

Books list

1. Planning from literature for grades 5-9 of general secondary schools. - T .: 2004. - 24 p.
2. State educational standard of general secondary education. //Public education j. 1999. No. 5. 6–36 p.
3. Husanboeva Q. Fundamentals of teaching independent thinking in literary education. - T.: Uzinkomsentr, 2003. - 103 p.
4. <http://xs.uz/uzkr/post/otkan-kunlar-ibrati>
5. [https:// n.ziyouz. com/portal-aqida/map/articles /N aim- K arimov- A bdulla- Q odiriy-komusi](https://n.ziyouz.com/portal-aqida/map/articles/Naim-Karimov-Abdulla-Qadiri-komusi)